

METHODS OF USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION AND ITS BENEFITS

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Abstract: this article examines the role of computers and computer programs in education and modern society, as well as a number of thoughts and opinions about this topic.

Key words: computer, computer technology, programs, electronic textbooks, personal computer, pedagogical program.

There are so many things going around the world these days. It is one of the simple cases that progress is made over the years and every field is improved and every field is improved. As long as the world and people exist, there are needs, and these needs are met in different ways. First of all, you need to live, to live you need to eat, and to eat you need to find food, and for this you must work. This food and living also cause the need. There are many such needs. Previously, food was prepared by chopping wood with an ax and lighting a fire through stones, but now this process has been improved and it is enough to press the gas button to cook. About 50 years ago, a well was dug to meet the need for water, but now, if you turn on a simple tap, you can get clean drinking water. Wells were also used to store meat products, and now refrigerators fulfill this task. There are many real-life examples of such development processes. There are more and more techniques that help people to lighten their weight. One of them is a computer. Not only computers, but also all technical tools and gadgets created by human hands. Examples of such tools are cars, airplanes, telephones, computers and their programs. The computer was originally designed in such a large size that it filled an entire large hall. It was not possible to relocate them elsewhere. The first computer weighed 27 tons. And he was able to perform more than 300 multiplications in one second. It was mainly designed to make bombs easier to make during the war. Over time, computers began to be used in other areas. Covers all areas of computing. And they began to reduce its size. Many people are interested in this technique and work on it for a long time to develop again and personal computers are born. Almost all actions can be performed in them. In terms of size, personal computers have been created that are small in size but have a lot of memory and functions. It would not be wrong to say that the 21st century is the century of electronics and technology. Today, all fields are connected with the computer and everything is easier with it. Computers help a lot by providing transparency in work and study. For example: in the hospital, there were various complaints during the queue waiting process, but this is being solved with the computer, that is, the whole process has been made online. Now you don't have to wait in line, you can make a reservation at the hospital through a convenient phone at home, the computer will tell you what time it is and what time it will be in the queue. You will easily reach this time. Now regarding the field of education: special evaluation programs have been developed so that the human factor does not participate in the issue of evaluation in schools, which ensures transparency and trust. Teachers can present the information they find useful and want to convey to the students to the whole class through the computer. Or

they can prepare presentations at home and make students more interested in the lesson process. It is known that several years ago schools were closed due to the virus. At that time, the computer came to the rescue and education was provided to children online. If they were not satisfied with the lessons, they did not have the opportunity to go to the website of their choice and read the necessary information. It is clear that the computer plays an important role in the educational process.

New information technologies are of great importance for the educational process and scientific research. In contrast to the usual educational technologies, information technology serves as the subject of work and its result, and the technical means of informatization serve as the tool of work.

Pedagogical technology has the following features:

1. Pedagogical technology is considered a factor of meeting the social need for improvement and optimization of the pedagogical institution.
2. Pedagogical technology is a set of theoretical and practical knowledge of a didactic and educational nature, as well as a set of theoretical and practical knowledge on organizing an educational institution in an effective and skillful manner, a methodological science.
3. Pedagogical technology is a holistic institution that reflects the general essence of an educational institution.
4. Pedagogical technology acts as a guide, that is, it serves to develop, educate, and shape a person.
5. Pedagogical technology has the character of personality, and there are no single, strict, normative requirements for the use of certain technologies in an educational institution. Each pedagogue has the ability to implement a certain technological approach, taking into account the characteristics of the educational environment in which he operates, existing internal and external conditions.
6. Pedagogical technology expresses the unity of education, training and personal development (maturity).

After the Republic of Uzbekistan achieved its independence, it firmly took its rightful place in the world community and development progress, and also entered the 21st century - the age of information technologies and the information society with rapid steps. Therefore, the role of informatics and information technologies in today's advanced education process is extremely incomparable. Today, for every pedagogue, these information technologies should play the leading role in his educational development. Because the development of the lesson should be clearly explained in the minds of young students. Only in this way, education will be formed in the minds of students in a more qualitative and enjoyable way.

CONCLUSION

In today's world, the use of modern technologies gives us several opportunities listed above. The qualification level of the population naturally plays an important role in the development of the country's economy, as well as in the formation of a democratic society and the social and spiritual development of the nation. The student's level of knowledge and mastery of science is reflected in the independent assignments he completes. , is useful in solving technical, production, economic, social, cultural tasks.

References:

1. Akhmedov, B. A., Makhkamova, M. U., Aydarov, E. B., Rizayev, O. B. (2020). Trends in the use of the pedagogical cluster to improve the quality of information technology lessons. Экономика и социум, 12(79), 802-804.
2. Akhmedov, B. A., Majidov, J. M., Narimbetova, Z. A., Kuralov, Yu. A. (2020). Active interactive and distance forms of the cluster method of learning in development of higher education. Экономика и социум, 12(79), 805-808.
3. Akhmedov, B. A., Eshnazarova, M. Yu., Rustamov, U. R., Xudoyberdiyev, R. F. (2020). Cluster method of using mobile applications in the education process. Экономика и социум, 12(79), 809-811.

